

Kinetics and mechanism of chloramine-T oxidation of glycolic acid catalysed by Pd^{II} complex in alkaline medium

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Abstract : The kinetics of chloramine-T (CAT) oxidation of glycolic acid (GA) using alkaline solution of palladous chloride complex as homogeneous catalyst has been investigated at 308 K. A 1 : 1 stoichiometry has been observed. The reaction shows first-order kinetics at lower [CAT] but at its higher concentration first-order tends to zero order. A first-order dependence of the reaction on both [GA] and [Pd^{II}] was observed. An increase in the concentration of OH⁻ ions increased the reaction rate, while addition of chloride ions decreased the rate of reaction. Added *p*-toluene sulphonamide (reduction product of chloramine-T) did not influence the reaction rate while zero effect of variation of ionic strength of the medium was observed. The overall activation parameters have been calculated from the Arrhenius plot. Mechanistic steps are suggested and the rate law derived was found in agreement with the observed kinetic results, stoichiometry and the reaction products.

Keywords : Kinetics, oxidation, chloramine-T, glycolic acid, Pd^{II} chloride, mechanism.

Introduction

Sodium salt of *N*-chloro-*p*-toluene sulphonamide (chloramine-T) is a very important member of aromatic sulphonyl haloamides. The diverse nature of the chemistry of such compounds is due to their ability to act as a source of halonium cations, hypohalite species and *N*-anions, which act as both bases and nucleophiles. As a result, these reagents react with large number of functional groups effecting an array of molecular transformations. Chloramine-T acts as an oxidizing agent in both acidic and alkaline media¹. The redox potential^{2,3} of chloramine-T/RNH₂ (where RNH₂, the reduction product of chloramine-T is *p*-toluene sulphonamide) is pH dependent and decreases with increase in pH of the medium. Generally, chloramine-T (CAT or RNCINa, where R = *p*-CH₃C₆H₄SO₂) undergoes a two electron change in its reactions. Depending on pH of the medium, CAT furnishes different types of reactive species in solution such as RNHCl, RNCl₂, HOCl and possibly H₂OCl⁺ in acid solutions and RNCI⁻ and OCI⁻ ions in alkaline medium⁴. This potent oxidant is of special interest for studying reaction mechanism as it behaves as both a chlorinating

and oxidizing agent⁵. It has been used widely for the quantitative direct and indirect determination of a large number of inorganic and organic compounds⁶. Although kinetic studies of uncatalysed reactions involving CAT as oxidant⁷⁻¹¹ have been made but few kinetic studies of catalysed CAT oxidations are reported¹²⁻¹⁶.

Glycolic acid works as an exfoliating agent because of its high acidity and easy solubility. Its about 10% solution has ability to draw moisturizers into newly exfoliated skin surface and thus it makes more youthful appearance.

The kinetics of redox reaction¹⁷⁻¹⁹ involving transition metal ions as homogeneous catalyst have found great potential applications in industrial growth as well as in understanding the biological properties of transition metal complexes. There seems to be few reports on the Pd^{II} complex as homogeneous catalyst. The oxidation of glycolic acid by chloramine-T is very slow in alkaline medium. In view of scant kinetic information about catalytic reactivity, biological properties and potential applications of complexes of Pd^{II} chloride, as well as due to importance of chloramine-T in industries, an attempt has been

made to study the kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of glycolic acid by chloramine-T using Pd^{II} chloride as catalyst in alkaline medium with main aims to ascertain (a) the reactive species of chloramine-T in alkaline medium, (b) reactive species of Pd^{II} chloride, (c) the role of Cl⁻ in deciding the catalytic species of Pd^{II} chloride and finally (d) to elucidate the mechanistic paths and derive the rate law consistent with kinetic results.

Experimental

The reagents employed were glycolic acid (E. Merck), palladous chloride (Johnson & Matthey) and chloramine-T (E. Merck, A.R. grade). All other reagents were of A.R. grade. All solutions of the reagents were prepared in doubly distilled water. The prepared solution of chloramine-T was standardized iodometrically. The stock solution of palladous chloride was prepared by dissolving its 1 g sample in HCl solution (0.02 mol dm⁻³). The concentration of Pd^{II} chloride and HCl were noted in the final stock solution. In order to prevent any photochemical decomposition, the solutions of chloramine-T and Pd^{II} chloride were stored in black coated bottles. The reaction bottles were also coated black from outside to avoid any photochemical effect. Sodium perchlorate was used to maintain the desired ionic strength of the medium.

The appropriate volumes of solutions of chloramine-T, sodium hydroxide, Pd^{II} chloride, potassium chloride and sodium perchlorate were taken in a reaction vessel. The volume of doubly distilled water was added to the reaction mixture to make up total volume of the reaction mixture 100 mL after adding requisite volume of solution of glycolic acid. The vessel containing the reaction mixture was kept inside the electrically operated thermostat maintained at the desired temperature ($\pm 0.1^\circ$ C). The reaction was initiated by adding the required volume of solution of glycolic acid (which too was thermally equilibrated at the same temperature) to the reaction vessel.

The kinetics of the reaction was followed by determining the unconsumed chloramine-T by withdrawing aliquots (5 mL) at regular time intervals iodometrically for two half-life periods of the reaction. The rate of reaction ($-dc/dt$) in each kinetic run was calculated with the help of the slope of the tangent drawn at fixed [chloramine-T] in the plot of unconsumed [chloramine-T] vs time. The order of reaction with respect to each reactants was

calculated by the relationship between the initial rate ($-dc/dt$) and concentration of each reactants.

Different experiments with varying [GA] : [RN NaCl] ratios were performed at 35 °C for 72 h under the experimental conditions [GA] \ll [RN NaCl]. Estimation of unconsumed [RN NaCl] in different sets indicated that one mole of GA consumes one mole of chloramine-T. Accordingly, the following stoichiometric equation can be written :

where R = CH₃C₆H₄SO₂

The reaction product formaldehyde was identified by spot test, when 1 mL of Schiff's reagent was added to 1 mL of the reaction mixture, a magenta colour rapidly developed in cold indicating presence of formaldehyde as reaction product.

Results and discussion

The kinetic studies were carried out at several initial reactant concentrations. The rate of the reaction ($-dc/dt$) increases linearly in low concentration range of chloramine-T (from 4.00×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³ to 12.00×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³) but in its higher concentration range (from 16.00×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³ to 25.00×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³) there is departure from linearity. This shows that first-order kinetics at low [RN NaCl] tends to zero-order at its higher concentration. This observation is also clear from nearly constant values of first-order rate constant (k_{obs}) at low [RN NaCl] and at higher [RN NaCl] decrease in values of k_{obs} , which is calculated by the formula,

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{(-dc/dt)}{[\text{RN NaCl}]}$$

The first-order rate constant (k_{obs}) increases linearly with increase in both [GA] and [Pd^{II}], indicating first-order dependence in both glycolic acid and Pd^{II} under the experimental condition (Table 1).

Table 2 contains the data showing the effects of variation of [OH⁻] and addition of potassium chloride and *p*-toluene sulphonamide (PTS). Positive effect of [OH⁻]

Table 1. Effect of variation of [CAT], [GA] and [Pd^{II}] on the rate of reaction at 35 °C

[CAT] × 10 ⁴ (mol dm ⁻³)	[GA] × 10 ² (mol dm ⁻³)	[Pd ^{II}] × 10 ⁶ (mol dm ⁻³)	<i>k</i> _{obs} × 10 ⁴ (s ⁻¹)
4.00	2.00	18.00	6.40
5.00	2.00	18.00	6.36
8.00	2.00	18.00	6.22
10.00	2.00	18.00	6.48
12.00	2.00	18.00	6.45
16.00	2.00	18.00	5.08
20.00	2.00	18.00	4.94
25.00	2.00	18.00	4.00
10.00	0.50	18.00	1.58
10.00	1.00	18.00	3.20
10.00	1.50	18.00	4.78
10.00	2.00	18.00	6.48
10.00	2.50	18.00	8.14
10.00	3.00	18.00	9.72
10.00	4.00	18.00	13.08
10.00	2.00	4.50	1.60
10.00	2.00	9.00	3.26
10.00	2.00	13.50	4.28
10.00	2.00	18.00	6.48
10.00	2.00	22.50	8.00
10.00	2.00	27.00	9.74

Under the conditions of [NaOH] = 1.00 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³; [KCl] = 1.00 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³.

variation was observed in its concentration range 0.50 × 10⁻² to 3.00 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³. A negative [Cl⁻] effect was observed. Addition of PTS did not influence the rate. This is also evident from nearly constant *k*_{obs} values at different [PTS]. Variation of ionic strength (*I*) from 1.10 × 10⁻² to 6.60 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³ shows negligible effect on rate of reaction. The reaction was studied in 30–40 °C temperature range and activation energy (*E*_a), entropy of activation (Δ*S*[#]) and free energy of activation (Δ*G*[#]) calculated from the rate measurements at these temperatures are given in Table 3.

The reaction mixture containing acrylamide and all other reagents under the conditions of Table 1 was kept in an inert atmosphere for 48 h. When methanol was added to the reaction mixture, precipitate was not found. Absence of formation of precipitate indicates that free radical is not formed and thus test for the formation of free radical in the reaction was found negative.

Table 2. Effect of variation of [OH⁻], [Cl⁻] and addition of [PTS] on the rate of reaction at 35 °C (Unless otherwise stated)

[OH ⁻] × 10 ² (mol dm ⁻³)	[KCl] × 10 ³ (mol dm ⁻³)	[PTS] × 10 ³ (mol dm ⁻³)	<i>k</i> _{obs} × 10 ⁴ (s ⁻¹)
0.50	1.00	–	4.16
1.00	1.00	–	6.48
1.50	1.00	–	7.00
2.00	1.00	–	8.36
2.50	1.00	–	9.64
3.00	1.00	–	11.48
1.00	0.50	–	7.54
1.00	1.00	–	6.48
1.00	1.50	–	4.96
1.00	2.00	–	3.92
1.00	3.00	–	3.00
1.00	4.00	–	2.60
1.00	1.00	0.50	6.46*
1.00	1.00	1.50	6.45*
1.00	1.00	2.50	6.42*
1.00	1.00	4.00	6.48*
1.00	1.00	6.00	6.45*
1.00 ^a	1.00	–	4.64
1.00 ^b	1.00	–	10.20
1.00 ^c	1.00	–	15.15

Under the conditions of [CAT] = 10.00 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³, [GA] = 2.00 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³, [Pd^{II}] = 18.00 × 10⁻⁶ mol dm⁻³, [CAT] = 12.50 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³ (*[PTS] variation); Temp. 30° (a), 40° (b) and 45° (c).

Table 3. Activation parameters of [Pd^{II}] catalysed oxidation of [GA] by [RN NaCl] in alkaline medium under the conditions of Tables 1 and 2 at 35 °C

Parameters	Values
<i>k</i> ₁ × 10 ⁻² (mol ⁻² dm ⁶ s ⁻¹)	2.60
<i>E</i> _a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	65.96
Δ <i>S</i> [#] (JK ⁻¹)	6.19
Δ <i>H</i> [#] (kJ mol ⁻¹)	63.37
Δ <i>G</i> [#] (kJ mol ⁻¹)	61.49
<i>A</i> × 10 ⁻¹³ (mol ⁻¹ dm ³ s ⁻¹)	3.66

Chloramine-T behave like a strong electrolyte²⁰ and ionises in aqueous solution as :

where R = CH₃C₆H₄SO₂- group

It has been reported¹⁴ that in aqueous alkaline solution, chloramine-T is hydrolysed as :

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